

Simulator attempt to install in infinite loop when get "ALL_PARSE_FAILED_NO_CERTIFICATES: Failed to collect certificates" error #2

New issue

Closed

Owner ...

With corrupted file: F-Droid_f35baa5a.apk, with bad signature:

```

kevenmen@node0:~/ApkVulFuzz/Evaluation-SSBSE-2026/seeds$ apksigner verify F-Droid_f35baa5a.apk
DOES NOT VERIFY
ERROR: APK Signature Scheme v3 signer #1: APK integrity check failed. CHUNKED_SHA256 digest mismatch. Expected: <
kevenmen@node0:~/ApkVulFuzz/Evaluation-SSBSE-2026/seeds$

```

Droidbot is hanged:

```

WARNING:DroidBotAppConn:Restarting droidbot app
43515
[CONNECTION] ADB is enabled and connected.
[CONNECTION] TelnetConsole is not enabled.
[CONNECTION] DroidBotAppConn is enabled and connected.
[CONNECTION] Minicap is not enabled.
[CONNECTION] Logcat is enabled and connected.
[CONNECTION] UserInputMonitor is enabled and connected.
[CONNECTION] ProcessMonitor is enabled and connected.
[CONNECTION] DroidBotIme is enabled and connected.
Please wait while installing the app...
adb: failed to install /users/kevenmen/ApkVulFuzz/Evaluation-SSBSE-2026/seeds/F-Droid_f35baa5a.apk: Failure [INST

```

Please wait while installing the app...
[CONNECTION] ADB is disconnected
[CONNECTION] Logcat is disconnected
[CONNECTION] UserInputMonitor is disconnected
Please wait while installing the app...
[CONNECTION] DroidBotIme is disconnected
[CONNECTION] ProcessMonitor is disconnected

This leads to a hang. Not sure if it is a security issue in practice.

Assignees
No one assigned

Labels
blackbox fuzzing droidbot hang

Projects
No projects

Milestone
No milestone

Relationships
None yet

Development
Code with agent mode

No branches or pull requests

Participants

added hang last

Owner Author ...

[F-Droid_f35baa5a.zip](#)
[F-Droid.zip](#)

added droidbot blackbox fuzzing 3 weeks ago

mentioned this 3 weeks ago
Issues with Corrupted Apps honeynet/droidbot#1

Owner Author ...

Reported. Nothing is needed now from our side; closing this issue.

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